

Study of the interaction between CO₂ and complex metal hydrides

María Laura Grasso ^b, Julián Puszkziel ^b, Martin Dornheim ^c, Claudio Pistidda ^c, Luisa Fernández Albanesi ^{a,b} and Fabiana Gennari ^{a,b}

^a Comisión Nacional de Energía Atómica-Instituto Balseiro, Ezequiel Bustillo 9500, 8400-Bariloche, Argentina

^b Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas, Godoy Cruz 2290, C1425-Buenos Aires, Argentina

^c Department of Nanotechnology, Institute of Materials Research, Helmholtz-Zentrum, Max Planck 1, 21502-Geesthacht, Germany

E-mail: grassomarialaura@gmail.com

The continue increase of CO₂ emissions from anthropogenic sources and their effects over the environment make it urgent to develop new technological options to reduce or mitigate CO₂ emissions. One alternative is the capture, storage and conversion of CO₂, which can be transformed in other valuable products such as methane, alcohols and plastics [1]. The methanation of CO₂ was first reported by Sabatier et al. They showed that CO₂ in the feed gas can be removed to produce methane and water during the ammonia synthesis. Also it is known that the reduction of CO₂ to CH₄ has important kinetic restrictions, and requires the use of a catalyst to achieve an acceptable rate and selectivity [2]. On this way, hydrogen storage alloys could be an attractive alternative to the classical catalysts for CO₂ methanation and at the same time, provide enough hydrogen for the reaction [3,4].

In this work, the potential of Mg₂FeH₆ and Mg₂NiH₄ complex hydrides for the conversion of CO₂ was explored under static conditions. The obtained results show that magnesium based-metal hydride containing Fe and Ni catalyses the hydrogenation of CO₂ with optimal experimental conditions at 400°C during 5 h and 10 h, respectively (see Fig.1). This study goes in depth in the use of Mg₂FeH₆ and Mg₂NiH₄ as hydrogen source and also the catalyst for the selective CO₂ reduction to CH₄ under mild conditions.

Figure 1: FTIR of gaseous phase products for Mg₂FeH₆-CO₂ (A) and Mg₂NiH₄-CO₂ (B)

References:

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